

Tetiarioa - ABS Agreement

Tetiarioa Biocode & Omic Observatory

Tetiarioa Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) Agreement	2
Article 1. AGREEMENT	3
Article 2. DEFINITIONS	3
Article 3. MANAGEMENT OF MATERIALS	3
Article 4. PUBLICATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS	4
Article 5. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT	4
Article 6. COMMERCIAL USE OF MATERIALS	5
Article 7. NOTICES	5
Article 8. TERM OF AGREEMENT	6
Exhibit A. MTA Between TS and Partner Institutions	7
Article 1. AGREEMENT	7
Article 2. DEFINITIONS	7
Article 3. MANAGEMENT OF MATERIALS	8
Article 4. PUBLICATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS	9
Article 5. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT	9
Article 6. COMMERCIAL USE OF MATERIALS	9
Article 7. NOTICES	10
Article 8. TERM OF AGREEMENT	10
Exhibit B: MTA Between Biocode Repositories and Third Parties	12
Article 1. DEFINITIONS	12
Article 2. USE OF MATERIALS	13
Article 3. TRANSFER OF MATERIALS	13
Article 4. PUBLICATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS	13
Article 5. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT	14
Article 6. COMMERCIAL USE OF MATERIALS	14
Article 7. ADDITIONAL TERMS	14
Article 7. NOTICES	15
Article 8. TERM OF AGREEMENT	15

Tetiaroa Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) Agreement¹

BETWEEN FRENCH POLYNESIA AND THE TETIAROA SOCIETY

THIS AGREEMENT [insert reference identifier] is between French Polynesia (“French Polynesia”) and Tetiaroa Society (“TS”)

- o In view of the organic law n°2004-192 of the 27th of February 2004, concerning the self-government status of French Polynesia and the law n°2004-193 of the 27th of February 2004 completing the self-government status of French Polynesia;
- o In view of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) concluded at Rio de Janeiro on 5 June 1992 and its Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization, which entered into force on 12 October 2014.
- o In view of the Conservation and Stewardship Agreement: Frangipani-TBSA-TS
- o Etc.

WITNESSETH:

- 1) WHEREAS within the context of the CBD, French Polynesia has the legal authority to prior informed consent and authorization to access and use the biodiversity of French Polynesia;
- 2) WHEREAS the owners of Tetiaroa have designated Tetiaroa Society the environmental steward of Tetiaroa charged with developing and implementing the Tetiaroa Conservation and Sustainable Use Plan (hereinafter the “CASUP”) including the responsibility for managing access to the genetic resources of the atoll, whether for non-commercial or commercial purposes.
- 3) WHEREAS the Tetiaroa Society has established the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Genomic Observatory** (hereinafter the “Observatory”), a scientific research program in collaboration with [INSERT] with the following objectives:
 - (i) to comprehensively inventory the biodiversity of Tetiaroa (French Polynesia), including all species of fauna and flora – plants, animals, algae, fungi, and microbial groups;
 - (ii) to generate time-series biodiversity observations at the molecular level, including DNA sequencing and other “multi-omic” approaches².
 - (iii) to test new technological and scientific approaches for the analysis of biodiversity patterns and ecological processes in general; and
 - (iv) to make Materials and information available to the research community.
- 4) WHEREAS the Observatory presents a unique opportunity to improve global scientific knowledge and to provide local benefits for French Polynesia by further understanding the biodiversity and ecological processes of Tetiaroa, and by supporting local management and development initiatives (notably the Tetiaroa CASUP), including training and public outreach activities in French Polynesia;

¹ Modified from the Moorea Biocode Project ABS Agreement

² Davies et al. Founding Charter of the Genomic Observatories Network. GigaScience 2014, <http://www.gigasciencejournal.com/content/3/1/2>

- 5) WHEREAS French Polynesia and TS are committed to implementing the letter and spirit of the CBD in carrying out the Observatory;
- 6) WHEREAS TS is responsible for administering the CASUP and managing the Observatory.

IT IS AGREED AS FOLLOWS:

Article 1. AGREEMENT

French Polynesia and the TS (hereinafter “the Parties”) agree that this Agreement represents prior informed consent for access to and mutually agreed terms for the use of the Materials collected on Tetiaroa and its surrounding waters in French Polynesia by TS and its Partner Institutions under the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Genomic Observatory**.

Article 2. DEFINITIONS

The Definitions used in this Agreement are as follows:

- a) **Materials** are the flora, fauna and microbial life obtained from French Polynesia under the Observatory, and any progeny, cell extract, genetic material or any other Unmodified Derivative thereof. Materials also include any Materials contained or incorporated in Modifications.
- b) **Modifications** are created substances that contain/incorporate the Materials.
- c) **Commercial Use** means commercial product development; the sale, lease, or license of the Materials; using the Materials to produce or manufacture products for general sale, not including publications and/or copyrightable works; transferring tangible rights by sale or license resulting in payment beyond cost; conducting market research; seeking pre-market approval.
- d) **Unmodified Derivatives** are substances created by TS that constitute an unmodified functional subunit or product expressed by the original Material. Some examples include: subclones of unmodified cell lines, purified or fractionated subsets of the Material, proteins expressed by DNA/RNA contained in the Material, or monoclonal antibodies secreted by a hybridoma cell line of the Material.
- e) **Inventions** are new uses of the Materials, Unmodified Derivatives or Modifications that are potentially commercially useful
- f) **Partner Institutions** are the organizations that TS designates as its key collaborators in the Observatory. Initially, they include [INSERT]. Additional partners may be designated by TS at any time.
- g) **Biocode Repositories** are units of TS or a Partner Institution that maintain biological collections and will act as custodians of the Materials collected by the Observatory.
- h) **Transfers** are when a Biocode Repository provides Materials to another party without any obligation or expectation that the other party will return the Materials intact and entire to the Biocode Repository.
- i) **Loans** are the traditional practice of natural history museums to temporarily exchange specimens for scholarly research that does not involve damaging or destroying any of the Materials. The specimens are returned intact and entire to the loaning institution. Loans are not considered Transfers of the Materials.

Article 3. MANAGEMENT OF MATERIALS

TS agrees to:

- a) Collect biological samples in accordance with the laws and regulations of French Polynesia;

- b) Process and store Materials at the Tetiaroa Ecostation and transfer them to other Biocode Repositories using the Material Transfer Agreement attached as Exhibit A (hereinafter “Biocode Repository MTA”);
- c) Inform French Polynesia if it transfers materials to a Biocode Repository of a new Partner Institution;
- d) Take all appropriate, reasonable, and necessary measures to transport (export and import) the Materials in accordance with relevant laws and regulations and to contain the Materials so as to prevent the release of invasive alien species;
- e) Only use the Materials for scientific research, education, and conservation purposes;
- f) Not distribute, transfer, or use the Materials for Commercial Use without prior approval of French Polynesia;
- g) Make information about the samples, the location of Materials, and scientific results publicly available. For example, through the iSamples infrastructure, including the Genomic Observatories Metadatabase (GEOME), and other global biodiversity informatics networks, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the Consortium for the Barcode of Life (CBOL), and the INSDC (“Genbank”);
- h) Transfer the Materials for non-Commercial Use to non-Biocode Repositories (e.g., third party scientific institutions, units of TS and its Partner Institutions that are not Biocode Repositories, and French Polynesia) using the terms and conditions of the Material Transfer Agreement attached as Exhibit B (hereinafter “Biocode Third Party MTA”).
- i) Maintain retrievable records of all transfers of Materials, and on request, will provide French Polynesia with records of such transfers;
- j) Return the Materials to French Polynesia if TS is unable or unwilling to continue its custodial role of storing the Materials for research and educational use.

Article 4. PUBLICATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

- a) This Agreement will be published in a publicly accessible online database and given a unique digital object identifier (DOI).
- b) TS shall be free to publish the results of its research activities using the Materials in scholarly publications and agrees to acknowledge in all publications and published reports the origin of the Materials from French Polynesia and the contribution of the Observatory, by making reference to this Agreement and its DOI.
- c) TS shall endeavor to make all reports or publications resulting from research on the Materials available to French Polynesia. For example, through iSamples / GEOME, the Tetiaroa Ecostation website, and IDEA Consortium (Tetiaroa IDEA) online resources.

Article 5. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT

- a) In the event that a patent application is filed for an Invention, TS shall promptly supply French Polynesia with a copy of the disclosure that French Polynesia shall hold in confidence and use only for evaluation purposes.
- b) Prior to any Commercial Use of an Invention, TS must agree to terms for sharing any financial benefits with French Polynesia.
- c) The provision of the Materials to TS shall not alter any pre-existing right to the Materials.

Article 6. COMMERCIAL USE OF MATERIALS

- a) Nothing in this Agreement grants TS any rights under patents, nor any rights to use any products or processes derived from or with Materials, for profit-making or commercial purposes.
- b) Sale or licensing of copyrighted works (such as documents) related to the Materials (e.g., photos of specimens, books, and scientific articles) is not considered Commercial Use of the Materials.
- c) The Materials may be used or transferred by TS for Commercial Use only after French Polynesia provides approval and terms for the use or transfer. It is understood by the Parties that such Commercial Uses may require a commercial license from French Polynesia to use the Materials or any part of the Materials that is incorporated in a Modification. It is understood by TS that French Polynesia shall have no obligation to grant such a license to TS and may grant exclusive or non-exclusive commercial licenses to others, or sell or assign all or part of the rights in the Materials to any third party(ies), subject to any pre-existing rights held by others.

Article 7. NOTICES

Notices to French Polynesia shall go to:

Legal Notices

Presidence De La Polynesie Française

Ministère de l'Education, de l'Enseignement supérieur et de la Recherche

Technical Communications

CBD Focal Point for French Polynesia

[French Polynesia to specify]

Notices to TS shall go to:

Legal Notices

Stanley Rowland

Tetiaroa Society

President

Technical Notices

Neil Davies, Ph.D.

Tetiaroa Society

Science Director

ndavies@moorea.berkeley.edu

Article 8. TERM OF AGREEMENT

This Agreement will terminate thirty (30) days after the recorded delivery of a written notice by either party to the other. The notice shall include an explanation of the reason for termination. The terms of use of any Materials already in TS's possession under this Agreement shall survive termination.

Done in 4 (four) original copies, two in English and two in French, both linguistic versions being of equal legal value.

French Polynesia	Tetiaroa Society
By _____	By _____
Name	Name
Title	Title
Date	Date

Exhibit A. MTA Between TS and Partner Institutions

This **Material Transfer Agreement** (“Agreement”), dated as of _____ (the “Effective Date”), is made by and between the Tetiaroa Society (“TS”), and [“Partner Institution Name”]

WHEREAS, TS desires that the Materials obtained by the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory** (the “Materials”) be used in academic research and that [Partner Institution Name] will provide custodial, research and storage facilities for the Materials and will provide Materials under their control to qualified Third Party Recipients (“Third Party Recipients”)

WHEREAS, TS will provide the Materials to [Partner Institution Name] and [Partner Institution Name] is willing to accept such Materials and is subject to the terms contained in this Agreement.

Article 1. AGREEMENT

TS and [“Partner Institution Name”] (hereinafter “the Parties”) agree that [“Partner Institution Name”] is a “Partner Institution” in the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory** and will maintain Materials as a “Biocode Repository” as defined in the **Tetiaroa ABS Agreement**. Materials are provided by TS to [Partner Institution Name] which has custodial responsibility for those Materials.

Article 2. DEFINITIONS

The Definitions used in this Agreement are as follows:

- a) Materials are the flora, fauna and microbial life obtained from French Polynesia under the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory**, and any progeny, cell extract, genetic material or any other Unmodified Derivative thereof. Materials also include any Materials contained or incorporated in Modifications.
- b) Modifications are created substances that contain/incorporate the Materials.
- c) Commercial Use means commercial product development; the sale, lease, or license of the Materials; using the Materials to produce or manufacture products for general sale, not including publications and/or copyrightable works; transferring tangible rights by sale or license resulting in payment beyond cost; conducting market research; seeking pre-market approval.
- d) Unmodified Derivatives are substances created by TS that constitute an unmodified functional subunit or product expressed by the original Material. Some examples include: subclones of unmodified cell lines, purified or fractionated subsets of the Material, proteins expressed by DNA/RNA contained in the Material, or monoclonal antibodies secreted by a hybridoma cell line of the Material.
- e) Inventions are new uses of the Materials, Unmodified Derivatives or Modifications that are potentially commercially useful

- f) Partner Institutions are the organizations that TS designates as its key collaborators in the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory**. Initially, they include: the Smithsonian Institution, Délégation à la Recherche de la Polynésie Française, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, University of Florida, Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Herbier de la Polynésie Française, and Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes. Additional partners may be designated by TS during the Project.
- g) Biocode Repositories are units of TS or a Partner Institution that maintain biological collections and will act as custodians of the Materials collected by the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory**.
- h) Transfers are when a Biocode Repository provides Materials to a second party without any obligation or expectation that the second party will return the Materials intact and entire to the Biocode Repository.
- i) Loans are the traditional practice of natural history museums to temporarily exchange specimens for scholarly research that does not involve damaging or destroying any of the Materials. The specimens are returned intact and entire to the loaning institution. Loans are not considered Transfers of the Materials.

Article 3. MANAGEMENT OF MATERIALS

The Materials will only be stored and used by [Partner Institution Name] for non-commercial scientific research, education, and conservation purposes. Further, [Partner Institution Name] will:

- a) Take all appropriate, reasonable, and necessary measures to transport (export and import) the Materials in accordance with relevant laws and regulations and to contain the Materials so as to prevent the release of invasive alien species;
- b) Only use the Materials for scientific research, education, and conservation purposes;
- c) Not distribute, transfer, or use the Materials for Commercial Use without prior approval of French Polynesia;
- d) Make information about the samples, the location of Materials, and scientific results publicly available. For example, through global biodiversity informatics networks, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF);
- e) Transfer the Materials for non-Commercial Use to non-Biocode Repositories (e.g., third party scientific institutions, units of TS and its Partner Institutions that are not Biocode Repositories, and French Polynesia) using the terms and conditions of the Moorea Biocode Agreement’s “Third Party MTA”.
- f) Maintain retrievable records of all transfers of Materials, and on request, will provide French Polynesia with records of such transfers;

- g) Return the Materials to French Polynesia if [Partner Institution Name] is unable or unwilling to continue its custodial role of storing the Materials for research and educational use.

Article 4. PUBLICATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

- a) This Agreement may be published in a publicly accessible online database and given a unique digital object identifier (DOI).
- b) [Partner Institution Name] shall be free to publish the results of its research activities using the Materials in scholarly publications and agrees to acknowledge in all publications and published reports the origin of the Materials from French Polynesia and the contribution of the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory**, by making reference to the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory Agreement** and its digital object identifier (DOI).
- c) [Partner Institution Name] shall endeavor to make all reports or publications resulting from research on the Materials available to French Polynesia. For example, through the online Biocode Portal and the Moorea Ecostation websites.

Article 5. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT

- a) In the event that a patent application is filed for an Invention, [Partner Institution Name] shall promptly supply French Polynesia with a copy of the disclosure that French Polynesia shall hold in confidence and use only for evaluation purposes.
- b) Prior to any Commercial Use of an Invention, [Partner Institution Name] must agree to terms for sharing any financial benefits with French Polynesia.
- c) The provision of the Materials to [Partner Institution Name] shall not alter any pre-existing right to the Materials.

Article 6. COMMERCIAL USE OF MATERIALS

- a) Nothing in this Letter Agreement grants [Partner Institution Name] any rights under patents, nor any rights to use any products or processes derived from or with Materials, for profit-making or commercial purposes.
- b) Sale or licensing of copyrighted works (such as documents) related to the Materials (e.g., photos of specimens, books, and scientific articles) is not considered Commercial Use of the Materials.
- c) The Materials may be used or transferred by [Partner Institution Name] for Commercial Use only after French Polynesia provides approval and terms for the use or transfer. It is understood by the Parties that such Commercial Uses may require a commercial license from French Polynesia to use the Materials or any part of the Materials that is incorporated in a Modification. It is understood by [Partner Research Institution Name] that French Polynesia shall have no obligation to grant such a license to [Partner Institution Name] and may grant exclusive or

non-exclusive commercial licenses to others, or sell or assign all or part of the rights in the Materials to any third party(ies), subject to any pre-existing rights held by others.

Article 7. NOTICES

Notices to French Polynesia shall go to:

Legal Notices

Presidence De La Polynesie Française

B.P. 255 1 ,98713 Papeete - TAHITI, Polynésie française- caserne Broche, Avenue Bruat

TCl. : (689) 47 20 00,

Technical Communications

Focal Point for French Polynesia

[FP to supply]

Notices to TS shall go to:

Legal Notices

Technical Notices

Notice to [Partner Institution Name] shall go to:

Legal Notices

[Partner Institution to supply]

Technical Notices

[Partner Institution to supply]

Article 8. TERM OF AGREEMENT

This Agreement will terminate thirty (30) days after the recorded delivery of a written notice by either party to the other. The notice shall include an explanation of the reason for termination. The terms of use of any Materials already in [Partner Institution Name]'s possession under this Agreement shall survive termination.

Done in 4 (four) original copies, two in English and two in French, both linguistic versions being of equal legal value.

Accepted and agreed

Partner Institution Name

TS

By:

By:

Name:

Name:

DRAFT – for discussion purposes

Title:
Date:

Title:
Date:

Exhibit B: MTA Between Biocode Repositories and Third Parties

The terms and conditions described in this **Material Transfer Agreement** (MTA) apply to Materials obtained from French Polynesia under the Tetiaroa ABS Agreement between the Tetiaroa Society (TS) and French Polynesia. They govern the transfer and use of those Materials from a Biocode Repository (“Provider”) to a third party [“Recipient”].

WHEREAS, Provider has custodial responsibility as a Biocode Repository for the Materials obtained from French Polynesia by the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory**; and

WHEREAS, Provider will provide Materials to the Recipient for limited non-commercial research or teaching purposes and only subject to the following terms and conditions:

Article 1. DEFINITIONS

Definitions used this Agreement are as follows:

- a) Materials are the flora, fauna and microbial life obtained from French Polynesia under the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory**, and any progeny, cell extract, genetic material or any other Unmodified Derivative thereof. Materials also include any Materials contained or incorporated in Modifications.
- b) Modifications are created substances that contain/incorporate the Materials.
- c) Commercial Use means commercial product development; the sale, lease, or license of the Materials; using the Materials to produce or manufacture products for general sale, not including publications and/or copyrightable works; transferring tangible rights by sale or license resulting in payment beyond cost; conducting market research; seeking pre-market approval.
- d) Unmodified Derivatives are substances created by TS that constitute an unmodified functional subunit or product expressed by the original Material. Some examples include: subclones of unmodified cell lines, purified or fractionated subsets of the Material, proteins expressed by DNA/RNA contained in the Material, or monoclonal antibodies secreted by a hybridoma cell line of the Material.
- e) Inventions are new uses of the Materials, Unmodified Derivatives or Modifications that are potentially commercially useful
- f) Partner Institutions are the organizations that TS designates as its key collaborators in the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory**.
- g) Biocode Repositories are units of TS or a Partner Institution that maintain biological collections and will act as custodians of the Materials collected by the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory**.

- h) Transfers are when a Biocode Repository provides Materials to another party without any obligation or expectation that the other party will return the Materials intact and entire to the Biocode Repository.
- i) Loans are the traditional practice of natural history museums to temporarily exchange specimens for scholarly research that does not involve damaging or destroying any of the Materials. The specimens are returned intact and entire to the loaning institution. Loans are not considered Transfers of the Materials.

Article 2. USE OF MATERIALS

Recipient shall use Materials for academic, non-commercial scientific research, education, or conservation purposes only. The Recipient shall:

- a) Take all appropriate, reasonable, and necessary measures to export and import the Materials in accordance with relevant laws and regulations and to contain the Materials so as to prevent the release of invasive alien species;
- b) Use the Materials only for the non-commercial research purposes (the “Research Project”) described in writing to the Provider prior to transfer, and not for any other purpose without the prior written consent of the Provider
- c) Shall not use Materials in research that is subject to consulting or licensing obligations to any third party without prior written approval of French Polynesia.
- d) Ensure that any Research Project using the Materials will be conducted in accordance with all existing laws and regulations;
- e) The Materials may not be further distributed to others without the prior written consent of the Provider. The Recipient will refer any request to Provider;
- f) Make information about the samples, the location of Materials, and scientific results publicly available. For example, through global biodiversity informatics networks, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF);

Article 3. TRANSFER OF MATERIALS

- a) This Agreement does not restrict Provider’s right to distribute the Materials and all Modifications and Unmodified Derivatives resulting thereof to other noncommercial entities.

Article 4. PUBLICATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

- a) Recipient shall be free to publish the results of its research activities using the Materials in scholarly publications and agrees to acknowledge in all publications and published reports the origin of the Materials from French Polynesia and the contribution of the **Tetiaroa Biocode & Omic Observatory** and the Provider, by citing the Tetiaroa ABS Agreement including its Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

- b) Recipient shall endeavor to make all reports or publications resulting from research on the Materials available to French Polynesia.

Article 5. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT

- a) In the event that a patent application is filed for an Invention, Recipient shall promptly supply French Polynesia with a copy of the disclosure that French Polynesia shall hold in confidence and use only for evaluation purposes.
- b) Prior to any Commercial Use of the Invention, Recipient must agree to terms for sharing any financial benefits with French Polynesia.
- c) The provision of the Materials to Recipient shall not alter any pre-existing right to the Materials.

Article 6. COMMERCIAL USE OF MATERIALS

- a) Nothing in this Letter Agreement grants Recipient any rights under patents, nor any rights to use any products or processes derived from or with Materials, for profit-making or commercial purposes.
- b) Sale or licensing of copyrighted works (such as documents) related to the materials (e.g., photos of specimens, books, and scientific articles) is not considered commercial use of the Materials.
- c)
- d) The Materials may be used by Recipient for Commercial Use only after French Polynesia provides approval and terms for these transfers. It is understood by the Parties that such Commercial Uses may require a commercial license from French Polynesia to use the Materials or that part of the Materials that is incorporated in the Modifications. It is understood by the Recipient that French Polynesia shall have no obligation to grant such a license to the Recipient and may grant exclusive or non-exclusive commercial licenses to others, or sell or assign all or part of the rights in the Materials to any third party(ies), subject to any pre-existing rights held by others.

Article 7. ADDITIONAL TERMS

- a) Any Materials delivered pursuant to this Agreement is understood to be experimental in nature and may have hazardous properties. The Provider MAKES NO REPRESENTATIONS AND EXTENDS NO WARRANTIES OF ANY KIND, EITHER EXPRESSED OR IMPLIED. THERE ARE NO EXPRESS OR IMPLIED WARRANTIES OF MERCHANTABILITY OR FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE.
- b) Except to the extent prohibited by law, the Recipient assumes all liability for damages that may arise from its use, storage or disposal of the Materials. The Provider will not be liable to the Recipient for any loss, claim or demand made by the Recipient, or made against the Recipient by any other party, due to or arising from the use of the Materials by the Recipient, except to the extent permitted by law when caused by the gross negligence or willful misconduct of the Provider.

- c) This Agreement is not assignable.

Article 7. NOTICES

Notices to French Polynesia shall go to:

Legal Notices

Presidence De La Polynesie Française

B.P. 255 1 ,98713 Papeete - TAHITI, Polynésie française- caserne Broche, Avenue Bruat

TCl. : (689) 47 20 00,

Fax. : (689) 43 15 62

Email : capr@presidence.pf

<http://www.presidence.pf>

Ministère de l'Education, de l'Enseignement supérieur et de la Recherche

B.P. 255 1 , 9871 3 Papeete - TAHITI, Polynésie française- Bâtiment administratif, Avenue Bruat

TCl. : (689) 47 24 40

Fax. : (689) 85 57 77

Technical Communications

Focal Point for French Polynesia

[FP to supply]

Article 8. TERM OF AGREEMENT

This Agreement will terminate on the earliest of the following dates: (1) on completion of Recipient's current research with the Materials, or (2) on thirty (30) days written notice by either party to the other. Paragraphs 2, 5 and 6 shall survive termination.